

**AEROELASTIC CONTROL OF COMPRESSOR BLADES IN TRANSONIC FLOW
USING PLASMA ACTUATORS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present work is to assess numerically the effectiveness of plasma actuators for controlling the aeroelastic response of a compressor cascade in transonic flow conditions. The potential suitability of such actuation for subsonic flows has been proved by the authors in previous works. Consistently with the approach employed for subsonic flows, pairs of actuators are located on the trailing edge of the blades, on the pressure side (PS) and on the suction side (SS). Actuators are operated to generate an induced flow either in the direction or against the freestream – setups referred to as downstream and upstream actuation, respectively. Computations at constant angle of attack with either PS or SS actuation are carried out first, to investigate the effects of plasma on the mean behavior of the flow and of the airloads. Subsequently, traveling wave pitch mode simulations for the clean and actuated cascade are performed. It is shown that properly triggered alternate PS/SS actuation – and adequate body force – can effectively reduce vibratory loads and enhance the aeroelastic stability of the cascade.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for lighter and more efficient aero engines has significantly grown during the last few years. To achieve this goal, modern compressors have been conceived with increasingly larger pressure ratio per stage. Natural consequences of these solutions are an aggressive blade loading and high flutter sensitivity, especially for long and slim blades. Blade design approaches aiming specifically at improving the aerostructural stability have been proposed [1, 2]. Also the aerodynamic performance is significantly affected on such highly loaded blades. Indeed, larger pressure gradients over the blade suction surface may anticipate the stall onset, therefore degrading the overall compressor performance. Diverse active flow control techniques have been proposed to optimize the aerodynamic performance of heavily loaded blades. Solutions like flow blowing, blades with adjustable angle of attack, movable leading edge, Gurney flaps, and adaptive camber – usually driven by piezo-actuators or shape memory alloys – have been proved to have a significant effect on the developed airloads [3–8].

Large interest has been lately addressed towards plasma

actuation. The suitability of plasma actuators stems from their lightness, and their non-intrusiveness in the flow field. Additionally, the absence of mechanical parts avoids the risk of structural and operational failures, likely to occur under high centrifugal loads typical of aero engines. Several numerical and experimental assessments have been carried out to investigate the effects of plasma actuators installed on heavily loaded blades on the resulting aerodynamic performance. It has been proved that appropriate locations and actuation strengths allow the suppression of spike stall inception [9], pressure loss reduction [10], and corner stall separation control [11]. In [12–15], plasma actuators have been first investigated as a means for controlling the aeroelastic response of compressor blades in subsonic flow conditions. It is found that properly phased alternate PS/SS actuations – with symmetrical effects for downstream and upstream induced flow – can reduce effectively the oscillation peaks in the unsteady airloads and increase the aeroelastic stability of the cascade for traveling wave pitch mode oscillations.

The present work aims to assess the operation of plasma aeroelastic control in transonic flow conditions, closer to the actual operation environment of aero engine compressors. This motivates the need of getting insights into the aeroelastic control capabilities of the plasma in a high-speed environment, and how it differs from the low-speed counterpart. Actuators are operated to generate an induced flow against the freestream or in the direction of the freestream. These two operation modes are referred to as upstream and downstream plasma actuation, respectively. A further application for the active control solution proposed here is represented by pressure-gain combustion engines¹. Indeed, these conceptual engines are characterized by huge oscillations in the pressure field. Therefore, blades are exposed to high level of vibration and enhanced risk of flutter, similarly to the modern blades designed for classical isobaric combustion engines.

The manuscript is articulated as follows. The second section provides a description of the computational fluid dynamic model. The numerical geometry, the grid and the plasma modeling are illustrated. The features of the numerical solver, alongside the specific settings employed for the present work, are also presented. The third section discusses the results at constant angle of attack. The flow field and the loads obtained on the clean and on the actuated cascade – with PS or SS actuation – are presented. Several angles of attack are taken under consideration. The sensitivity of the airloads to the plasma body force is also assessed. Comparisons between the results obtained with upstream and downstream plasma actuation are provided. The fourth section deals with traveling wave pitch mode simulations. Computations are carried out in the whole interblade phase angle range. Actuators are operated

alternately on the PS and on the SS during the pitching oscillation cycle of the cascade. The unsteady flow field obtained with upstream and downstream plasma actuators is reported and discussed in detail. The effectiveness of the actuation on the cascade aeroelastic stability is assessed by computing the aerodynamic damping – a non dimensional parameter defining the net work flux between the flow and the blade. An estimation of the plasma body force needed to achieve a stable cascade for the whole range of interblade phase angles is given. Consistently with the approach adopted for constant angle of attack computations, both upstream and downstream actuations are considered. Final remarks are given in the last section.

COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS MODEL

The simulations here performed use the linear cascade at the Chair for Aero Engines at the Technische Universität (TU) Berlin. Specific experimental features of this aeroelastic instrumented cascade are found at [16]. The numerical domain is sketched in Fig. 1, depicting seven NACA 65 profiles set up with a stagger angle of 43° . The pitch-to-chord ratio is 0.75, while the blade chord length is $c = 0.15m$. The cascade is a low-speed setup, and in previous works [12–15], numerical results were compared and validated against experiments. In the current study, this geometry is used in a high-speed setup, which is currently not realized experimentally. The goal is to change the boundary conditions to a more turbomachinery-realistic environment, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of plasma actuation. In this manner, clear-cut comparisons can be done to the previous studies.

FIGURE 1: Compressor linear cascade simulated numerically.

The boundary conditions for the current high-speed case correspond to cruise-flight atmospheric conditions, which would be encountered by a fan or low-pressure compressor stage. Total pressure and temperature are set at the inlet, along with the flow direction (enabling easy changing of the angle of attack α). At the outlet, a static pressure value is set to induce both subsonic velocities at the inlet and outlet, but inducing sonic areas around the blades. The values are shown in Tab. 1. Indeed, with an increase in α , sonic regions develop initially at the SS leading edge, but after a localized shock, subsonic flow takes place again. Close to the trailing edge,

¹This type of engine is currently under study at the TU Berlin within the Collaborative Research Center 1029 (CRC 1029), funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. The present work is part of the subproject B01 of CRC 1029.

though, no shocks are present in the clean (no actuation) case. The presence of sonic regions (due to flow field only) close to the actuators would make the analysis much more intricate, lying beyond the scope of the current work.

Inlet	
Total pressure	32.7 kPa
Static temperature	216.7 K
Angle of attack (α)	0° to 10°
Mach number	0.6 to 0.9
Reynolds number	$6.2 \cdot 10^5$

Outlet	
Static pressure	25.0 kPa
Mach number	0.62
Mass flow	0.31 kg/s

TABLE 1: Boundary conditions for transonic simulations.

The solver Ansys CFX [17] is employed for the calculations. The compressible viscid medium is modeled with the RANS two-equation Menter's $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model [18]. Rhie and Chow fourth-order pressure dissipation smoothing is applied [19]. Convergence is accelerated by a multigrid solving approach.

3D computations with span-wise uniform plasma have highlighted that the flow remains substantially two-dimensional. Therefore, 2D simulations are performed in the present work. The meshes are generated with Ansys ICEM CFD. Detailed information about grid independence study for the current setup is explained in detail in [14, 15], so only the main aspects are presented here. 550949 hexaedra cells are arranged in structured blocks, with an O-grid enclosing each airfoil. The wake and plasma actuation regions are extra refined to accurately model the physics of the problem. Figure 2 depicts the computational grid employed for the present computations. Low-Reynolds computations are carried out, keeping the non-dimensional wall distance $y^+ \approx 2$, below the buffer layer. Between 10 and 20 cells are located on the boundary layer adjacent to the blade surface.

The time discretization is carried out with a second order backward Euler march. A time discretization independence study was performed, similarly to the procedure described in [14, 15]. Since now the flow speed is definitely higher than the low-speed counterpart of the previous works, smaller time steps are required to properly resolve the high frequency flow phenomena. The time resolution sensibility was particularly

FIGURE 2: Detail of the computational grid around the blade (top), zoomed in close to the trailing edge (bottom).

investigated when calculating the aerodynamic damping (further defined) for a case with upstream plasma actuation, as shown in Fig. 3, for interblade phase angle equals 0. The relative variation in the aerodynamic damping between the last two discretization setups (400 and 500 time steps per oscillation period) is less than 0.5%. The middle value (300) also seemed to be quite independent from further time discretization, but to investigate more in detailed the flow phenomena, further unsteady runs were performed with 400 time steps per oscillation period.

FIGURE 3: Aerodynamic damping parameter Ξ obtained for upstream plasma actuation for several time resolutions. 400 time steps per oscillation period were employed in the simulations.

The essential effect of plasma actuators is to add momentum into the flow field and in turn to modify the local velocity profile [10]. Therefore, the force field generated by the actuators is introduced as a source term to the momentum Navier-Stokes equation integrated by the solver. Consistently with several studies [9, 20–22], plasma actuators are modeled as rectangular regions, tangent to the airfoil trailing edge, both on the PS and on the SS. A schematic of the blade geometry with actuators is shown in Fig. 4. The downstream actuation path is sketched, the upstream counterpart having a tangentially opposite actuation direction. Plasma actuators are modeled in the three central blades of the cascade to capture the effects of adjacent plasma-equipped units.

FIGURE 4: Schematic view of plasma actuators installed tangentially to the blade surface.

In this work, body forces in the range $[0, 33750]$ mN/m, i.e. $[0, 33.750]$ N/m, are employed as momentum sources. Several studies have been carried out to assess the effect of geometrical, material and voltage input properties of plasma actuators on exerted body force and induced velocity profiles. For instance, Thomas et al. [23] investigated experimentally the body force induced by plasma actuators featuring different sizes and dielectric materials, fed with a wide range of voltage amplitudes and frequencies. The exerted body force was found to increase with the voltage amplitude. Notice that while the required input voltage for the actuators is rather high – usually in the order of several kV –, the power consumption remains limited, as the current needs are bounded to few mA. For the purposes of the present work, the maximum power required is approximately 100 W.

The higher the freestream velocity, the larger the body force has to be. Indeed plasma-induced momentum must be comparable to the one of the baseline flow. Only in this way it is possible to obtain an effective operation of plasma and an adequate manipulation of the flow field. The momentum generated by plasma actuators on the flow – determined by the body force – is the major challenge of plasma actuators to be operated in actual aeronautical applications. Important advancements have been accomplished in this regard, since the early plasma actuation concepts [24–26]. The work of Porter et al. [25], dating back to 2006, shows that the body forces issued by plasma actuators have grown by ten times with respect to early designs. It is therefore broadly acknowledged that in the next few years the body force generated by plasma actuators will grow remarkably further [9, 24–28].

These foreseeable improvements in plasma capabilities substantiate the present work, aiming at controlling a fully attached flow in transonic conditions. Higher body forces are required here, compared to the active control of separated flows. In fact, the recirculating areas associated with separated flows feature much smaller velocities relative to the freestream value. In the work of Gu [29], plasma actuators are assessed as a means to control lift on a wing of a commercial aircraft operating in realistic takeoff, cruising and landing conditions. Specifically, Gu performed numerical computations to assess the optimal plasma configuration – in terms of location and body force – to obtain effects comparable to those of mechanical Gurney flaps/ailerons on the wing of a Boeing 737 in different flight phases. The investigations of [29] consider freestream Mach numbers up to 0.84. Gu states that to “apply plasma

Gurney flap on the full-scale aircraft, the plasma Gurney flap needs to have an effective plasma actuation strength on the order of 25 – 70 N/m at high subsonic cruising conditions, and about 100 N/m at landing/takeoff conditions. The presence of shocks can help improving the effectiveness of plasma Gurney flap.” [29]. Gu [29] also states that for some configurations, several actuators are needed to achieve the desired effects, so that the total body force is even higher than the values employed in this work. In summary, estimated plasma body forces for real commercial aircraft applications are much larger than those available with current actuators. These argumentations are consistent with those of [9, 27, 28, 30], which investigated plasma flow control on aero engines in highly transonic conditions. Such situations have been shown to require body forces not yet achievable by current plasma actuators.

Improved dielectric materials and optimized input voltages are likely to become available in the next years, as also pointed out by [9, 27, 28]. The 100 N/m value suggested by Gu [29] for obtaining an adequate manipulation of airloads is one order of magnitude higher than the maximum body force employed in this work. It is also worth noting that the aeroelastic response of turbomachinery bladings is dominated by the interaction between the blades [31]. As a consequence, it is likely that a very limited number of actuators per annulus – potentially even a single plasma-equipped blade – are enough to control the aeroelastic response of the entire stator/rotor setup. This is a huge advantage in terms of power requirements, installation, and high-voltage sources. Within this framework, a detailed discussion of the possible implementation techniques, including retrieving the input voltage signals and solutions to avoid electromagnetic interferences has been given by the authors in previous works [14, 15, 32]. It is also worth recalling that plasma actuators might be designed thin and small enough to be installed on turbomachinery blades, see e.g. [10, 30]. Moreover the aero engine sections most exposed to vibratory loads and flutter risks are the fan, the first compressor stages and the last turbine stages [33]. The blades of these stages are certainly long and thick enough to enable the installation of large-size plasma actuators, i.e. up to approximately 7 cm total chordwise length [23]. Additionally, the driving parameters for the body force exerted by plasma actuators are the dielectric properties of the material, rather than the size of the device [23] – the latter playing only a secondary role. The actuators of [29], supposed to provide body forces up to 160 N/m, feature a total chordwise length of approximately 3 cm and a thickness smaller than 0.2 mm. Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that actuators with highly increased body force, as those needed for the present applications, should not be dramatically oversized compared to the current layouts.

Previously obtained low-speed results [12–15] highlight that PS upstream or SS downstream actuation enable an increase in the effective blade camber and a downward shift of the Kutta condition application point, i.e. an enlargement of the airfoil chord. This yields an enhancement

in lift and nose-down pitching moment, compared to the clean configuration. Opposite effects are encountered for SS upstream or PS downstream actuation. Namely, a negative camber is induced and reduction in lift and nose-down pitching moment is obtained. Neither upstream nor downstream actuations cause remarkable drag rises.

Analogously to [12–15], simulations are performed with the blades: i) in fixed position; ii) oscillating harmonically according to traveling wave pitch motions. For fixed blades computations, the effects on pressure distribution, airloads and flow field are assessed on the clean cascade and in PS and SS actuated cases. For traveling wave pitch motions, the actuated configuration features an alternate triggering of PS/SS actuation during the blade oscillating cycle. Specifically, for downstream actuation, PS plasma is triggered during the upstroke phase of the blade pitching motion (nose moving upward). Conversely, SS downstream plasma is triggered during the downstroke phase of the blade pitch motion (nose moving downward). The opposite triggering is adopted for upstream actuation. That is, PS plasma is switched on during the downstroke phase of the pitching cycle, whereas SS plasma is triggered during the upstroke phase of the motion.

For the unsteady calculations, the blade pitchwise displacement is prescribed according to Eq. 1:

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 + \bar{\alpha} \sin(2\pi ft + n\sigma), \quad (1)$$

being the angle of attack $\alpha(t)$ the sum of a mean angle $\alpha_0 = 2^\circ$ and a harmonic oscillation with amplitude $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$. A pitchwise oscillating frequency $f = 19.17\text{Hz}$ is used (matching the experimental torsion natural frequency), yielding a reduced frequency $k = 2\pi fc/U_\infty \approx 0.1$. Every blade is represented by an index $n = 1, \dots, 7$. The interblade phase angle σ is defined as positive when the traveling wave traverses the cascade from blade pressure towards suction side.

A displacement diffusion algorithm is used to carry out the mesh movement [34]. For that, a diffusion equation $\nabla \cdot (\Gamma_{\text{disp}} \nabla \delta) = 0$ is solved at every time step, where δ is the relative displacement with respect to previous mesh positions and Γ_{disp} the mesh stiffness. In this way, the general mesh topology is preserved.

The effects of alternate PS/SS actuation (downstream and upstream) are investigated in terms of aerodynamic loads and local flow field. Moreover the effects of actuation on the aerodynamic damping Ξ are assessed. This quantity is the dimensionless counterpart of the aerodynamic work W_{aero} , and quantifies the aeroelastic stability of a system (for more details, see e.g. [1, 35, 36]). The aerodynamic damping is defined in Eq. (2):

$$\Xi = -\frac{W_{\text{aero}}}{\pi q c^2 \bar{\alpha}^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $q = \frac{2}{\gamma Ma_\infty^2} \left(\frac{p}{p_\infty} - 1 \right)$ corresponds to the dynamic pressure of a compressible flow. Ma_∞ and p_∞ are the freestream Mach number and pressure values, respectively. γ is the gas heat capacity ratio. The aerodynamic work W_{aero} is obtained by the area integral on the blade section ℓ , further integrated in time t during one oscillating period $T = 1/f$, as in Eq. (3):

$$W_{\text{aero}} = \int_T \int_\ell p \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} d\ell dt, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the wall velocity vector, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ the wall outwards normal versor and p the static pressure. For $\Xi > 0$, a stable behavior is expected from the blade displacement; in other words, energy is being transferred from the structure into the flow. On the other hand, $\Xi < 0$ indicates that the blade motion is being positively fed with energy from the flow, hinting instability.

STEADY RESULTS

Angle of attack study

The angle of attack α was varied according to the range on the previously defined boundary conditions (Tab. 1). Actuation was activated independently both on PS and SS, with force per unit length given respectively by $A_{\text{PS}} = A_{\text{SS}} = 3000 \text{ mN/m}$. Upstream and downstream actuating directions were simulated to better understand their effects on the steady loads and pressure distribution. Lift, drag and half-chord moment coefficients are depicted in Fig. 5, along with clean cascade results. The trend with which the loads vary is quite similar to the low-speed actuation previously reported in [15]. The lift coefficient is increased for PS upstream and SS downstream actuation, decreasing for the other two instances. The drag coefficient slightly increases only for SS downstream actuation; however, as previously discussed, detailed drag assessments are beyond the current plasma implementation goals, since actuation energy input, 3D effects and more precise turbulence modeling would be recommended. Additionally, drag forces do not play a significant active role in the aerodynamic damping analyses.

The results for the half-chord moment differ modestly from the low-speed analogue. Initially, SS upstream actuation seems to impart a higher positive variation in the half-chord moment for the high-speed flow, while PS upstream does not convey significant change with respect to the clean case. Finally, all actuation setups lose strength for higher α . Since the simulated unsteady conditions are restricted to small angles of attack, this outcome for higher α should not be relevant for the current analyses. In general, the half-chord moment provides insight into which actuation setup could be optimally used for the unsteady operation, so to reduce pitching vibration and flutter instability ranges.

The pressure coefficient distributions for the clean and actuated steady setups are depicted in Fig. 6, for $\alpha = 2^\circ$

FIGURE 5: Force coefficients for clean case, upstream and downstream actuation, on pressure and suction side, as a function of angle of attack. Actuation body force $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 3000$ mN/m.

and $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 3000$ mN/m. Upstream and downstream distributions are shown separately in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b) respectively, for clarity. With respect to the upstream case (Fig. 6(a)), a clear change in the pressure is observed close to the trailing edge, where the pressure decreases on the surface where the actuator is located, but increases slightly right upstream. Additionally, an overall C_p increase on the entire blade surface is observed for SS actuation, in comparison to PS actuation. On the other hand, for downstream actuation (Fig. 6(b)), SS actuation conveys a general decrease in C_p . Finally, the evident effect of the plasma actuation close to the trailing edge in the upstream case is not particularly developed in the downstream actuation setups, where actually a narrow and localized pressure trough appears at the very end of the trailing edge. These results show that higher actuating forces may indeed change the pressure distribution perceptibly on the entire blade surface, up to the leading edge.

Actuation force study

With the aim of assessing how much actuation force is needed to change the airloads significantly in transonic conditions, the actuation directions and locations were varied independently. That is, steady runs were performed for both upstream and downstream, PS and SS actuation. The nondimensional velocity field for all actuation cases can be seen in Fig. 7, for $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 10000$ mN/m and $\alpha = 2^\circ$. The actuation effects on lift, drag and half-chord moment are depicted in Fig. 8, for $\alpha = 2^\circ$.

Regarding the lift coefficient, depicted on Fig. 8(a), downstream actuation reaches a plateau after the forcing approaches 3000 mN/m, meaning that further increase in downstream actuation does not impart significant change in C_l . This behavior differs from the low-speed case, where force increments up to almost 1000 mN/m conveyed a linear impact on the blade lift [15]. One trend, however, remains the same in the current high-speed setup: SS downstream actuation increases the lift, with opposite effect for PS downstream actuation.

On the other hand, upstream actuation changes the lift steadily and fairly linearly up to $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 10000$ mN/m, indicating that the upstream actuation should have a higher

FIGURE 6: Pressure coefficient C_p distribution on middle blade, for clean and actuated cases. Here, $\alpha = 2^\circ$ and $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 3000$ mN/m.

FIGURE 7: Nondimensional velocity field close to blade trailing edge for several actuation setups. Here, $\alpha = 2^\circ$ and $A_{PS} = A_{SS} = 10000 \text{ mN/m}$.

potential of acting on high-speed flows. Reversed outcomes (with respect to the downstream runs) are observed for the upstream case: SS actuation reduces the lift, while PS rises it.

The drag slightly increases for downstream actuation, in accordance with the low-speed results. Upstream actuation imparted a small reduction in drag. These results are shown in Fig. 8(b).

The half-chord moment plays an important role in the aerodynamic damping of pitch-moving blades, being shown in Fig. 8(c). The configurations that most affect the moment coefficient are the ones acting on the SS. Upstream actuation induces additional nose-down moment. Conversely, downstream actuation provides nose-up pitching moment. These results motivate the alternating use of PS and SS actuation with proper phasing with respect to up- and

FIGURE 8: Airloads as a function of actuation force, for clean case, upstream and downstream cases, at $\alpha = 2^\circ$.

downstroke stages of the blade displacement. A nonlinear response of moment with respect to forcing is obtained for PS actuation, where the moment rate of change even changes sign for high actuation loads.

UNSTEADY RESULTS

Following the steady characterization of the plasma actuation in a high-speed environment, the unsteady results are presented in the current section. As previously stated, the main goal of plasma actuation in the current work is to reduce/eliminate flutter instability regions on the operation range of the linear cascade in focus. For that, alternating actuation on PS and SS is employed, following the conclusions collected from the steady airloads (see Figs. 5 and 8).

The unsteady upstream actuation is implemented in the following fashion: active on the PS during downstroke

phase (leading edge going down, or section moving counterclockwise); active on the SS during upstroke phase (leading edge going up, or section moving clockwise). This choice is motivated by the shifts observed in the half-chord moment (Figs. 5(c) and 8(c)), as previously discussed. The opposite actuation phasing is carried out for downstream computations. The reasoning is to impart a moment in the opposite direction of the blade rotational velocity, in order to obtain an arithmetically negative contribution for the aerodynamic work (W_{aero} in Eq. (3)) and therefore a positive - stabilizing - contribution for the aerodynamic damping parameter (Ξ in Eq. (2)).

The actuation intensity was set to influence the surface-adjacent flow in a similar magnitude on both PS and SS. The same actuation ratio $A_{\text{PS}}/A_{\text{SS}} = 0.5$ from the low-speed case was kept. A parametric unsteady force run-up was performed to determine the minimum necessary force to impart stability along the entire σ range for upstream actuation. The force per unit length necessary was $A_{\text{PS}} = 16875$ mN/m and $A_{\text{SS}} = 33750$ mN/m, clearly higher than for the low-speed counterpart.

The aerodynamic damping parameter Ξ is depicted as a function of interblade phase angle in Fig. 9, for the clean and actuated cases. The stable and unstable regions (according to the energy method) are also marked. With respect to the clean cascade curve, instability is expected in almost the entire negative interblade phase angle range. This result differs from the low-speed case, where only a small σ extent yielded negative Ξ , specifically close to $\sigma = 50^\circ$ [15]. This area still coincides with the minimum aerodynamic damping observed for the high-speed runs.

Regarding the upstream actuated unsteady results, stability was achieved along the entire interblade phase angle range, with the present forcing values. The maximum value of Ξ is now more than three times the maximum value for the clean cascade. The interblade phase angle that promotes the least stability was shifted to zero, corresponding also to a zero nodal diameter condition.

With respect to the downstream unsteady actuation, no effective gain was obtained, from the flutter stability point of view. This outcome would not be expected analyzing only the half-chord moment steady values (Fig. 5(c)). However, as shown in Figs. 8, downstream actuation conveyed a limited, saturated effect in the airroads for high forces (e.g. Fig. 8(a)). Additionally, the flow areas affected by high force downstream plasma blowing extend farther aft the trailing edge, having clearly less impact on the loads developed around the blade surface (which in turn influence the aerodynamic damping). Therefore, downstream-directed actuators localized almost at the trailing edge were not able to remove the flutter instability areas as the upstream did. A potential solution would be to install the downstream actuators further upstream on the blade surface.

FIGURE 9: Aerodynamic damping parameter Ξ as a function of interblade phase angle σ . For upstream and downstream actuation, $A_{\text{PS}} = 16875$ mN/m and $A_{\text{SS}} = 33750$ mN/m.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work presented a numerical evaluation of a linear cascade with plasma actuation in transonic flow regime. The current high-speed results were contrasted with previous low-speed analyses performed with the same geometry, which represents the aeroelastic test rig at the Chair for Aero Engines at the Technische Universität Berlin.

The steady outcomes characterized how the plasma-equipped blades react to upstream and downstream actuation, both on the pressure and suction sides. The actuators, located close to the trailing edge, were able to significantly change the airroads on the blade surface. Particularly, the lift coefficient is increased for PS upstream and SS downstream actuation. The other setups promoted a reduction in lift. Regarding the half-chord moment, SS actuation seems to convey a stronger effect than PS. These results motivated the alternating activation of plasma on PS and SS in the unsteady runs.

Aiming at removing flutter-prone zones, unsteady computations were performed with the blades moving harmonically in the pitchwise direction (representing a torsion natural mode). Traveling wave assessments with the energy method showed the cascade to be aeroelastically unstable for negative interblade phase angles. These instability zones have been completely removed with upstream plasma actuation. The alternating plasma operation (PS during downstroke and SS during upstroke phase) was thus successful in reducing the energy transferred from the flow to the structure. It is important to remark that the forcing values were much higher than the low-speed counterpart, reaching $A_{\text{PS}} = 16875$ mN/m and $A_{\text{SS}} = 33750$ mN/m. Although some challenges still have to be addressed when practically implementing these high-forcing actuators, several improvements in this direction have been listed and discussed in the manuscript, encouraging the feasibility of this technology for vibration control and flutter prevention.

NOMENCLATURE

A	actuation force
a	local speed of sound
c	reference chord
C_p	pressure coefficient
C_l	lift coefficient
C_d	drag coefficient
$C_{m_{c/2}}$	half-chord moment coefficient
f	oscillation frequency
k	reduced frequency, $k = 2\pi f c / U_\infty$
Ma	Mach number, $Ma = U_\infty / a$
ν	kinematic viscosity
n	blade index
\hat{n}	surface normal versor
p	static pressure
q	dynamic pressure, $q = \frac{2}{\gamma M_\infty^2} \left(\frac{p}{p_\infty} - 1 \right)$
Re	Reynolds number, $Re = c U_\infty / \nu$
t	time
T	oscillation period
\mathbf{u}	velocity vector
U_∞	free stream velocity magnitude
W_{aero}	aerodynamic work
y^+	dimensionless wall distance
α	angle of attack
α_0	mean angle of attack
$\tilde{\alpha}$	pitch oscillation amplitude
δ	grid displacement relative to previous mesh locations
Γ_{disp}	mesh stiffness
σ	interblade phase angle
Ξ	flutter stability parameter

Abbreviations

CFD	computational fluid dynamic(s)
PS	pressure side
SS	suction side

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